

Habitat Connectivity Trends: Calculation, Modelling and Assessment

Vitalii Kriukov^{*1}, Lucy Bastin^{†1}, Riyad Rahman^{‡1}, Ivette Serral^{§2}
and Joan Maso^{**2}

¹Aston University, Birmingham, UK

²CREAF, Autonomous University of Barcelona, Spain

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Summary

A range of indices are available to calculate terrestrial habitat connectivity based on land-use/land-cover data. Two tools (Graphab and MiraMon) were used to create timeseries datasets (1987-2022) and build the pipeline to analyse trends in connectivity. Data4Land tool was developed to enrich LULC datasets with OpenStreetMap data. Habitat connectivity indices of forest-dwelling mammals and target species (*Testudo hermanni*) for Catalonia (Spain) were produced. In contrast to shrublands and meadows, forest connectivity mainly follows a positive trend, but considerable spatial differences are observed between Barcelona, protected areas and Pyrenees. The developed workflow supports decision-making and trade-offs between stakeholders in spatial planning.

KEYWORDS: spatial data, biodiversity, habitat connectivity, land-use/land-cover, spatial modelling

1. Introduction

In the face of global ecosystem changes, nature conservation is one of the main dimensions of environmental studies. Biodiversity challenges are amongst the most urgent topics in international and regional policies and declarations such as The Convention on Biological Diversity, Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (McGowan et al., 2024). At the same time, habitat connectivity is considered one of the key indicators of biodiversity at all scales (Perrin, Bertrand and Vanpeene, 2022; JNCC, 2024). However, no overarching indicator has been developed that is applicable to every study area, species, and available dataset. Graphab (Foltête J-C et al., 2021) and MiraMon ICT^{††} tools are amongst the most popular options, providing valuable statistics at various scales. Graphab computes indices based on graph theory such as Probability of Connectivity or Betweenness Centrality, whereas MiraMon provides pixel-by-pixel calculations for discrete points in LULC rasters.

2. Methods

As of now, connectivity computation workflow consists of the following steps:

1. Preprocessing of LULC raster datasets and their derivatives via Data4Land tool developed by the authors^{‡‡}
2. Habitat connectivity computations in Graphab and MiraMon software independently

* kriukovv@aston.ac.uk

† l.bastin@aston.ac.uk

‡ riyad23008@gmail.com

§ ivette@creaf.uab.ca

** joan.maso@uab.ca

†† MiraMon, ICT plugin: <https://www.mirammon.cat/help/eng/msa/ICT.htm> (Accessed on 30/01/2025)

‡‡ Data4Land software: <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2> (Accessed on 30/01/2025)

3. Analytical and statistical post-processing
4. Connectivity forecasting based on LULC change scenarios

Compared to the previous connectivity study (Kriukov et al., 2024), the 1987-2017 LULC timeseries which cover Catalonia developed through the automatic classification of Landsat and Sentinel-2 images (Gonzalez-Guerrero and Pons, 2020) have been extended up to 2022. Moreover, the study areas in Northern England based on Sentinel-2 LULC (Impact Observatory, 2017-2023) and the UKCEH datasets^{§§} has been analysed as well to validate the workflow.

Detailed analysis was conducted in Albera Natural Park located in the northeast of Catalonia adjacent to France. The case study is focused on *Testudo hermanni* which is heavily affected by the conversion of shrublands into vineyards (Capalleras et al., 2013), as well as invasive species, road infrastructure, global climate changes, and wildfires (Gracia et al., 2020).

3. Results

A positive trend for forest habitats is observed across Catalonia in 1987-2022 (**Figure 1**), but significant spatial distinctions were detected, e.g. the Pyrenees Mountain corridor and protected areas experienced positive dynamics (+3.5% in the Index of Terrestrial Connectivity, or ICT, in Catalonia and +3.8% in Pyrenees) whereas Barcelona metropolitan area has been steadily losing the corridors between woodland habitats (-7%). Even though the medium correlation between indices from Graphab and MiraMon exists, it is observed only within the patches of habitats. Graphab indices, except from the number of corridors, do not cover landscape beyond habitat, therefore, it is important to carry out both types of analysis while assessing the connectivity trends and estimating positive or negative effect from changes in land-use/land-cover.

Figure 1 Dynamics of the Index of Terrestrial Connectivity in Catalonia (produced in MiraMon)

According to preliminary analysis focused on the Albera Natural Park and neighbouring region, the 2012-2022 trend can be characterised as positive, highlighting the spreading of shrublands and transitional woodlands reflecting natural succession (**Figure 2**). Natural wildfires occur regularly in Catalonia, and this period was marked by considerable increase (from 37.3 to 44.8%, depending on the value of maximum distance parameter) in the Probability of Connectivity index from 2012 to 2017, while La Jonquera area was recovering after devastating fires in 2012 without additional human interventions. Therefore, significant number of ecological corridors between the Albera Natural Park and neighbouring habitats were burned down. It is also suggested that increasing habitat connectivity could contribute to the growing risk of forest fires in future (Bowen et al., 2007).

^{§§} UKCEH Land Cover Maps: <https://www.ceh.ac.uk/data/ukceh-land-cover-maps> (Accessed on 16/01/2025)

Figure 2 ICT index from MiraMon and ecological corridors from Graphab in 2012 (left), dynamics of probability of connectivity index from Graphab (right) in the Albera Natural Park and surroundings, case study of *Testudo hermanni* (2012-2022)

According to our analysis of vineyard distribution in the case study area, altitude, slope, and distance between new and old vineyards are the main factors (**Figure 3**), while the aspect of slope does not show high significance.

Figure 3 Distribution of altitude (left) and slope (center) within and near the Albera Natural Park, Catalonia in 2022. Based on a resampled global digital elevation model and its derivatives with a 30 m spatial resolution (SRTM, 2013)

4. Conclusion

The developed workflow provides a semi-automatic solution to calculate terrestrial habitat connectivity combining advantages of two different approaches to analyse existing trends and negative or positive effect of land-use/land-cover changes.

It is planned to extend this study by developing the preliminary analysis of vineyards' distribution in the north-eastern Catalonia, creating a multiple regression model and synthetic suitability map for *Testudo hermanni* which can be used to simulate scenarios of future land-use/land-cover transitions from natural and semi-natural shrublands, meadows, and woodlands to vineyards, and assess the negative effect for habitat connectivity.

Another ongoing case study is focused on *Erinaceus europaeus* (the European hedgehog) in Northern England, a species widely studied across the UK and considered one of the most prominent mammals endangered by habitat fragmentation and connectivity loss (App et al., 2022). This study is based on an extended LULC classification of the UKCEH Land Cover datasets, already enriched with the Data4Land tool.

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Biographies

Vitalii Kriukov — a Postdoctoral Researcher at Aston University, UK, focused on biodiversity, habitat connectivity, FAIR dataspace and spatial data harmonisation tools to provide stakeholders with trade-off decisions on land-use changes.

Lucy Bastin — a Professor in computer science and environmental informatics at Aston University, UK, previously worked at Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, Birmingham Urban Wildlife Trust and University of Leicester.

Ivette Serral — a GIS Technician at CREAM (Spain) focused on international geospatial standards, FAIR standards, various applications of GIS and remote sensing, including biodiversity conservation and chemical ecology.

Riyad Rahman – a Research Assistant at Aston University, experienced in full-stack software engineering primarily in the fields of GIS, harmonising data from air and water quality sensors.

Joan Maso — a Principal Investigator at CREAM (Spain) leading specialized group on geospatial interoperability, GIS, remote sensing, teacher in GIS and remote sensing (University of Barcelona), coordinator of the AD4GD Horizon project.